

First record of Greater Flamingo *Phoenicopterus roseus* from Peralam in Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary, Tamilnadu, South India

S.Ramasubramanian^{1*} and A.Kumaraguru²

¹ Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary, Nagapattinam, Tamil Nadu, South India.

² Biodiversity Conservation Foundation, Trichy, South India.

Abstract

This paper describes the first sighting of Greater Flamingo *Phoenicopterus roseus* inside the evergreen forest of Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary, Tamilnadu, South India. The possible use of these new record for devising conservation management plans for the Greater Flamingo is discussed.

Keywords: conservation, Greater Flamingos, *Phoenicopterus roseus*, Point Calimere, water birds.

The Point Calimere wetland complex of South India consists of 38,500 ha. of wetland area which includes Point Calimere wildlife sanctuary, the Great Vedaranyam wetland, Muthupet mangroves and Thalainayar Reserved Forest. Together the entire area was declared as Ramsar site in August 2002 as it fulfills all the nine important criteria required for declaring a Ramsar site (Baruah, 2005). There are two major forest types in the sanctuary viz., the tropical dry-evergreen forest and the open grass lands patches. A third forest type but occurring in lesser extent is the mangrove forests fringing the Muniappan Lake inside the sanctuary and parts of the sanctuary coast (Baruah, 2005). Nearly half the sanctuary is under evergreen forest and thickets.

The sanctuary is located along the Palk Strait in three districts of Tamil Nadu Nagapattinam, Tiruvarur and Thanjavur. It lies in between 10°17' - 10°22' N latitude and 79°25' - 79°52' E longitude, covering an area of 38,500 hectares from Point Calimere in the east to Adirampattinam in the west. The sanctuary is home to the largest population of the endemic Blackbuck (*Antelope cervicapra*) in South India (Baruah, 2006). A variety of 364 species of flowering plants including 198 species of medicinal plants have been recorded in the sanctuary (Baruah, 2006).

Point Calimere Wetland complex is famous for the large congregations of water birds, particularly the Greater Flamingos (Baruah, 2005 and 2006). The wetlands are important wintering grounds for water birds from north (Baruah, 2005 and 2006). Nearly 100 species of migratory water birds including the Greater Flamingo arrives at the sanctuary and its surroundings from September onwards and stays on till February before their return journey to north (Baruah, 2006). There are

two species of Flamingos viz., the greater (*Phoenicopterus roseus*) and lesser (*Phoeniconaias minor*). Flamingos are found in India (Ali and Ripley, 1983). The greater flamingo has the most widespread distribution of all flamingo species. Populations are found in northwest India, the Middle East, the western Mediterranean and Africa. Limited numbers of this species can be found over much of northern Europe and eastward to Siberia. The flamingo's most characteristic habitats are large alkaline or saline lakes or estuarine lagoons that usually lack vegetation. Lakes may be far inland or near the sea. (Flamingo, 2011).

The greater Flamingo visit Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary regularly (Baruah, 2005). Greater Flamingos are generally seen near the pump house area of Point Calimere while feeding and they use the vast expanse of mudflats from the pump house to Muthupet mangroves. They generally feed on microscopic water plants and animals. While feeding the birds lowers its beak upside down in the mud to sweep and seep to separate organic microbes with comb filters in its bill.

Greater flamingos arrive in the month of September and stay here till February end. They are sighted in the mudflats of Pump house area, Panchanadhikulam wetland and Great Vedaranyam swamp. They are neither documented nor seen inside the water bodies of dry evergreen forests of Point Calimere Sanctuary. Surprisingly, a flock of more than 60 Greater flamingos (Fig 1 & 2) are seen in the Peralam pond (Map.1) inside the dry evergreen forests on 22nd April 2013. The long-legged and long-necked individual with a hooked bill was first spotted by S.Ramasubramanian, IFS, Wildlife Warden, Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary, Nagapattinam, A.Senthilkumar, Naturalist & Wildlife Photographer of Biodiversity Conservation Foundation (BCF) and Dr.A.Kumaraguru, Conservation Scientist, BCF in the morning and then in the evening photographed by Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary

*Corresponding Author
email:rama_s2002@rediffmail.com

Map.1. A satellite view of Peralam Pond in Point Calimere Wildlife and Bird Sanctuary, South India.

biologist N. Balasubramaniam and A. Senthilkumar, BCF. In spite of summer, still some amount of water remains in the Peralam pond and these Greater flamingos are seen feeding in the pond. This is the first record of Greater Flamingo seen inside the dry evergreen forests where the pond remains a source of water. The availability of algal bloom and fishes at the Peralam pond might be the primary reason which provides ample food supply for Greater flamingos to inhabit the pond. The favourable features of the environment at Peralam has to be evaluated as a suitable habitat for greater flamingos which generally inhabit deep, salty and coastal lagoons. The dry evergreen forests with perching trees like *Manilkara hexandra*, *Calophyllum inophyllum* and *Cassia fistula* and mangrove plants such as *Avicennia officinalis* and *Clerodendrum inerme* can act as a suitable buffer for the wetland complex and offer enough feed in the small ponds inside the forests (Kumaraguru Pers. Comm).

There are numerous records on the sightings of greater flamingos, but still there is increasing need to understand the distribution pattern of these flamingos in this century marked by excessive anthropogenic pressures. Hence, incorporation of information on new sightings in a habitat will greatly help us to understand

the changes in the distribution pattern of flamingos with respect to changes in the environment. Therefore it is imperative to understand the habitat suitability for flamingos in Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary. This vital information would help the managers to prepare management plans for long term conservation of these species and protect the adjoining landscapes to ensure lean season feed requirements.

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